

FREQUENCY OF PERIPHERAL ARTERY DISEASE IN THE CASES PRESENTING WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

Dr. Hira Shaheen^{*1}, Birg ® Dr. Muhammad Tahir²

^{*1} Post Graduate Trainee, FCPS General Medicine, Punjab Rangers Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

² Professor / HOD, Internal Medicine Department, Study Supervisor, Punjab Rangers Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

^{*1}hirashaheen104@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17395229>

Keywords

Peripheral Arterial Disease, Diabetes Mellitus, Risk Factors, Ankle-Brachial Index.

Article History

Received: 06 March, 2025

Accepted: 16 March, 2025

Published: 22 March, 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Hira Shaheen

Abstract

Background: Due to inconsistent findings in existing literature regarding PAD frequency in diabetics, this study aimed to determine the actual burden, enabling early identification, anticipatory screening, and appropriate management to prevent serious vascular complications.

Objective: To determine the frequency of peripheral artery disease in the cases presenting with Diabetes Mellitus.

Duration: Six months w.e.f July 2024 till Dec 2024

Methodology: After approval of the synopsis and ethical review committee (ERC) approval, patients were informed about the study objectives and written consent was obtained. Detailed information on risk factors, including smoking, hypertension, and obesity, was recorded. Peripheral artery disease was diagnosed through ankle-brachial index measurements. All data were systematically collected using a structured proforma and analyzed with SPSS version 23.0 for statistical evaluation.

Results: The study included 237 diabetic patients with a mean age of 44.84 ± 9.87 years; 58.6% were aged 41–60 years, and 58.6% were male. PAD was present in 35.0% of patients. Higher PAD frequency was observed among smokers (40.0%), hypertensives (37.5%), obese individuals (36.2%), and females (35.7%), though differences were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Peripheral Artery Disease was identified in 35.0% of diabetic patients. Although slightly higher in certain subgroups, no significant differences were found. These findings support the need for routine screening to prevent complications and improve diabetic patient outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels resulting from insufficient insulin production by the pancreas or impaired insulin action in the body. It affects individuals of all ages and is typically a chronic condition that requires lifelong management through medication and lifestyle modifications.¹ Globally, the burden of diabetes is

significant and rising. In 2017, approximately 462 million people were affected by type 2 diabetes, representing 6.28% of the world's population, with prevalence rates of 4.4% among those aged 25-49 years, 15% in the 50-69 age group, and 22% in individuals aged 70 and above.² Diabetes accounted for over one million deaths annually, making it the ninth leading cause of mortality worldwide.³

Early diagnosis of type 2 diabetes is critical in preventing severe complications. However, symptoms can be mild or nonspecific, leading to delayed diagnosis and treatment³. Normally, after a meal, increased blood glucose stimulates insulin release from pancreatic beta cells. Insulin facilitates glucose uptake into muscle, adipose tissue, and liver cells by binding to insulin receptors, enabling cellular energy production.⁴ In type 2 diabetes, insulin resistance develops often due to sedentary lifestyle, obesity, or fat deposition near insulin receptors impairing glucose uptake and resulting in hyperglycemia⁵. Persistently elevated blood sugar causes beta cells to produce more insulin, which may eventually become insufficient to maintain glucose homeostasis.^{3,5}

Diabetes is associated with numerous complications affecting multiple organ systems. These include microvascular complications such as retinopathy, neuropathy, and nephropathy, as well as macrovascular complications, including coronary heart disease (CHD), cerebrovascular disease, and peripheral artery disease (PAD).^{6,7} Nonvascular complications may involve infections, skin changes, and sensory impairments. Furthermore, type 2 diabetes has been linked to cognitive decline and increased risk of dementia.⁸

Among these complications, PAD is a significant cause of morbidity. Studies report varying frequencies of PAD in diabetic populations worldwide. For example, a Danish study reported an incidence of 8.8%,⁹ whereas an Ethiopian study found a prevalence of 30.7%.¹⁰ Other studies reported PAD frequencies of 13.98% in Ecuador,¹¹ 8.52% in India,¹² 19.0% and 31.6% in Pakistan.^{13,14} These conflicting findings in the existing literature create uncertainty regarding the actual burden of PAD among diabetic patients. Therefore, this study was conducted to generate local data, clarify the frequency of PAD in a defined diabetic population, and support more effective screening, diagnosis, and preventive strategies.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted over six months at Punjab Rangers Teaching Hospital, Lahore, after obtaining ethical approval from the institutional review board. A sample size of 237

cases was calculated using a 95% confidence interval, 5% margin of error, and an expected prevalence of peripheral artery disease (PAD) of 19.0%.¹³ Patients aged 25 to 60 years, of either gender, diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (defined as HbA1c $\geq 7.0\%$) were enrolled through non-probability consecutive sampling. After obtaining informed consent, each participant's demographic details, including age and gender, were recorded. Relevant clinical risk factors such as smoking (more than 10 packs per week), hypertension (blood pressure $>140/100$ mmHg), and obesity (BMI >25) were documented. All participants underwent sonographic evaluation for PAD, and a diagnosis was made if the ankle-brachial index (ABI) was <0.9 , measured by a radiologist. Data were collected using a structured proforma and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Continuous variables such as age were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables including gender, smoking status, hypertension, obesity, and PAD presence were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Stratification was performed for age, gender, and risk factors, and post-stratification analysis was carried out using the Chi-square test, considering a p-value ≤ 0.05 as statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study included a total of 237 participants with a mean age of 44.84 ± 9.87 years. Among them, 41.4% (n=98) were between 25–40 years of age, while 58.6% (n=139) were in the 41–60 year age group. Males comprised 58.6% (n=139) of the sample, and females accounted for 41.4% (n=98). Regarding smoking status, 38.0% (n=90) of the participants were smokers, while 62.0% (n=147) were non-smokers. Hypertension was present in 57.4% (n=136) of the cases, and 42.6% (n=101) had no history of hypertension. The mean BMI was 26.66 ± 3.82 kg/m², with 35.9% (n=85) having a BMI of ≤ 25.0 and 64.1% (n=152) having a BMI >25.0 . Data is given in table 1.0. Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD) was present in 35.0% (n=83) of patients, while 65.0% (n=154) did not show evidence of PAD. This finding indicates a considerable frequency of PAD among individuals with diabetes mellitus, underlining the need for

early detection and management in this population, as shown in table 2.0.

Stratification of the data revealed that certain subgroups had a higher frequency of Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD), although the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). PAD was more commonly observed in the 41–60 year age group (36.7%) compared to the 25–40 year group (32.7%; $p = 0.521$). Females exhibited a slightly higher frequency of PAD (35.7%) than males (34.5%; $p =$

0.851). The frequency of PAD was also greater among smokers (40.0%) than non-smokers (32.0%; $p = 0.209$). Similarly, patients with hypertension showed a higher frequency (37.5%) compared to those without hypertension (31.7%; $p = 0.353$). In terms of body mass index, individuals with BMI >25.0 had a higher frequency of PAD (36.2%) compared to those with a BMI ≤ 25.0 (32.9%; $p = 0.616$) as given in table 3.0.

Table 1.0: Demographic Characteristics of Patients Presenting with Diabetes Mellitus

Characteristics	Total (n=237)
Age (years)	44.84±9.87
• 25-40 years	98 (41.4%)
• 41-60 years	139 (58.6%)
Gender	
• Male	139 (58.6%)
• Female	98 (41.4%)
Smoking	
• Yes	90 (38.0%)
• No	147 (62.0%)
Hypertension	
• Yes	136 (57.4%)
• No	101 (42.6%)
BMI	26.66±3.82
• ≤ 25.0	85 (35.9%)
• >25.0	152 (64.1%)

Table 2.0: Frequency of PAD in Patients Presenting with Diabetes Mellitus

Peripheral Artery Disease	Frequency, %
• Yes	83 (35.0%)
• No	154 (65.0%)

Table 3.0: Stratification of Frequency of PAD in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus Stratified for Sub Groups

Characteristics	PAD		p-value
	Yes	No	
Age (years)			
• 25-40 years	32 (32.7%)	66 (67.3%)	0.521
• 41-60 years	51 (36.7%)	88 (63.3%)	
Gender			
• Male	48 (34.5%)	91 (65.5%)	0.851
• Female	35 (35.7%)	63 (64.3%)	
Smoking			

• Yes	36 (40.0%)	54 (60.0%)	0.209
• No	47 (32.0%)	100 (68.0%)	
Hypertension			
• Yes	51 (37.5%)	85 (62.5%)	0.353
• No	32 (31.7%)	69 (68.3%)	
BMI			
• ≤25.0	28 (32.9%)	57 (67.1%)	0.616
• >25.0	55 (36.2%)	97 (63.8%)	

Chi Square test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

DISCUSSION

Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD) is a common yet often underdiagnosed complication in patients with diabetes mellitus.¹ Although certain subgroups, such as older age, smokers, and hypertensive individuals, showed a higher frequency of PAD in this study, the difference were not statistically significant. Existing literature presents conflicting evidence regarding the frequency and risk factors of PAD in diabetic populations, leading to controversy and uncertainty in clinical practice.^{9,14} Therefore, this study was conducted to better understand the genuine burden of PAD among diabetics. Identifying its frequency can support timely screening, anticipatory testing, and early interventions to reduce long-term vascular complications.

This study included 237 participants with a mean age of 44.84 ± 9.87 years, which is notably lower than the mean ages reported in several previous studies. For instance, Tyagi et al.¹⁵ in India reported a mean age of 58.21 ± 9.81 years, Bouragba et al.¹⁶ in Algeria found 57.58 ± 16.98 years, and Solangi et al.¹⁷ in Pakistan reported 52.59 ± 9.91 years, with only 29.2% of patients aged between 20–50 years and 70.8% above 50 years. Similarly, Ali et al.¹⁸ and Islam et al.¹⁹, both in Pakistan, reported mean ages of 60.5 ± 8.4 years and 51.1 ± 14.69 years, respectively. These differences in mean age may be attributed to variations in inclusion criteria, study design, and geographical populations across the studies.

In this study, males comprised 58.6% (n=139) of the sample, and females accounted for 41.4% (n=98). Previously male dominance in study cohort was reported by Ali et al.¹⁸ as 55.0% while inverse find signs were reported by Tyagi et al.¹⁵ where males were only 41.05 of the study sample.

Regarding smoking status, 38.0% (n=90) of the participants were smokers, while 62.0% (n=147) were non-smokers in this study. Ali et al.¹⁸ reported that 71.1% participants in their study were non-smokers, 20.1% were ex-smokers and 8.8% were current smokers.

In this study, hypertension was present in 57.4% (n=136) of the cases, and 42.6% (n=101) had no history of hypertension. Previously, in similar studies frequency of hypertension was reported as 65.2% and 46.7% by Solangi et al. and Ali et al.¹⁷, respectively.

The mean BMI in this study was 26.66±3.82 kg/m², with 35.9% (n=85) having a BMI of ≤25.0 and 64.1% (n=152) having a BMI >25.0. Previously mean BMI in such studies was reported as 25.45±3.9 kg/m² and 27.23±5.05 kg/m² by Tyagi et al.¹⁵ and Solangi et al.¹⁷, respectively. Islam et al.¹⁹ reported that 23.6% patients were normal weight, 49.1% were overweight and 27.3% were obese in their study.

In the present study, Peripheral Artery Disease (PAD) was identified in 35.0% (n=83) of diabetic patients. This frequency lies within the broader range reported in existing literature, which shows considerable variation across different regions and populations. For instance, a relatively low prevalence was reported by Kamil et al.⁹ in Denmark (8.8%), Arora et al.¹² in India (8.54%), and Barrearea-Guarderas et al.¹¹ in Ecuador (13.98%). In contrast, moderate frequencies were noted by Akalu et al.¹⁰ in Ethiopia (30.7%), Islam et al.¹⁹ in Pakistan (28.5%), and Khan et al.¹³ in Pakistan (19.0%). Higher prevalence rates have also been documented, including 31.6% by Akram et al.¹⁴, 38.0% by Solangi et al.¹⁷, both in Pakistan, and 47.1% by Bouragba et al.¹⁶ in Algeria. These variations may be attributed

to differences in study design, diagnostic criteria, population characteristics, and healthcare access across regions. The current study thus contributes valuable insight into the regional burden of PAD in diabetic patients, emphasizing the need for early screening and intervention.

CONCLUSION

Peripheral Artery Disease was observed in 35.0% of diabetic patients, indicating a substantial burden. While higher frequencies were noted in certain subgroups, no statistically significant differences were found. These results emphasize the need for regular screening and early management of PAD in diabetic populations to reduce future vascular complications.

LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

This study provides valuable regional data on PAD frequency among diabetic patients, highlighting trends across demographic and clinical subgroups. Its strengths include a well-defined sample and standardized diagnostics. Limitations involve its single-center, cross-sectional design and limited generalizability. Future multicenter and longitudinal studies should focus on subgroups showing higher PAD frequency such as older age, smokers, obese and hypertensive patients to better understand risk factors and tailor preventive strategies, ultimately improving outcomes in diabetic populations.

Conflict of Interest: None

Source of Funding: None

Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy

or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2

Substantial contributions to concept, study design

Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

REFERENCES

- Wu J, Huang J, Zhu G, Wang Q, Lv Q, Huang Y, et al. Elevation of blood glucose level predicts worse outcomes in hospitalized patients with COVID-19: a retrospective cohort study. *BMJ Open Diab Res Care*. 2020;8(1):e001476.
- Khan MAB, Hashim MJ, King JK, Govender RD, Mustafa H, Al Kaabi J. Epidemiology of type 2 diabetes-global burden of disease and forecasted trends. *J Epidemiol Glob Health*. 2020;10(1):107-11.
- Li Y, Guo L, Li L, Yang C, Guang P, Huang F, et al. Early diagnosis of type 2 diabetes based on near-infrared spectroscopy combined with machine learning and aquaphotomics. *Front Chemis*. 2020;8:580489.
- Yu J, Wang J, Zhang Y, Chen G, Mao W, Ye Y, et al. Glucose-responsive insulin patch for the regulation of blood glucose in mice and minipigs. *Nat Biomed Eng*. 2020;4(5):499-506.
- Suhariningsih S, Astuti SD, Husen SA, Winarni D, Rahmawati DA, Mukti AT, et al. The combined effect of magnetic and electric fields using on/off infrared light on the blood sugar level and the diameter of Langerhans islets of diabetic mice. *Vet World*. 2020;13(10):2286.
- Peters SA, Woodward M. Sex differences in the burden and complications of diabetes. *Curr Diab Rep*. 2018;18(1):1-8.
- Cloete L. Diabetes mellitus: an overview of the types, symptoms, complications and management. *Nurs Standard*. 2021;37(1):61-6.

- Huang HK, Liu PP, Lin SM, Hsu JY, Yeh JI, Lai EC, et al. Diabetes-related complications and mortality in patients with atrial fibrillation receiving different oral anticoagulants: a nationwide analysis. *Ann Intern Med.* 2022;175(4):490-8.
- Kamil S, Sehested TS, Carlson N, Houllind K, Lassen JF, N. Bang C, et al. Diabetes and risk of peripheral artery disease in patients undergoing first-time coronary angiography between 2000 and 2012—a nationwide study. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord.* 2019;19(1):1-9.
- Akalu Y, Birhan A. Peripheral arterial disease and its associated factors among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients at Debre Tabor general hospital, Northwest Ethiopia. *J Diab Res.* 2020;2020(1):9419413.
- Barrera-Guarderas F, Carrasco-Tenezaca F, De la Torre-Cisneros K. Peripheral artery disease in type 2 diabetes mellitus: survival analysis of an Ecuadorian population in primary care. *J Prim Care Commun Health.* 2020;11:2150132720957449.
- Arora E, Maiya AG, Devasia T, Bhat R, Kamath G. Prevalence of peripheral arterial disease among type 2 diabetes mellitus in coastal Karnataka. *Diab Metab Syndr Clin Res Rev.* 2019;13(2):1251-3.
- Khan AM, Lohana P, Anvekar P, Mustafa SH, Kumar R, Lnu A, et al. Risk factors of peripheral vascular disease in diabetes mellitus in Abbottabad, Pakistan: a cross-sectional study. *Cureus.* 2021;13(8):e17556.
- Akram J, Aamir AU, Basit A, Qureshi MS, Mehmood T, Shahid SK, et al. Prevalence of peripheral arterial disease in type 2 diabetics in Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2011;61(7):644-8.
- Tyagi V, Gupta A, Bansal N, Virmani SK. Prevalence of peripheral artery disease in diabetes mellitus. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2017;5(11):4881-5.
- Bouragba I, Diaf M. Association between peripheral arterial diseases and metabolic syndrome in patients with type 2 diabetes from northwestern Algeria. *J Postgrad Med Inst.* 2023;37(4):244-50.
- Solangi AH, Malik AK, Hussain K, Sadique Z, Rind SH, Aleem SA. Frequency of peripheral arterial disease among patients with type-ii diabetes mellitus presenting to a tertiary care hospital. *J Popul Ther Clin Pharmacol.* 2024;31(9):814-9.
- Ali N, Samiullah SM, Ahmed T, Shahzad RK. Frequency of peripheral arterial disease among diabetic patients. *Pak J Med Health Sci.* 2022;16(08):701-5.
- Islam UU, Din SU, Mumtaz A, Qasim M. Frequency of peripheral arterial disease in type-ii diabetic patients presenting with diabetic retinopathy. *Ann Punjab Med Coll.* 2022;16(4):326-9.